

The Impact of Implementing Kahoot! & Windows Shopping Learning Model on Learning Interest of Class X DKV1 SMK N 3 Surakarta Students in Basic DKV Subjects

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Abstract:

This research was conducted to find out the effect of implementing Kahoot! and the Windows Shopping learning model on the learning interest of class X DKV1 SMK N 3 Surakarta students in the Basic DKV subject. This is important because students' interest in learning is one of the determining factors for learning that has been designed to run effectively. The method used in this research is qualitative in the form of questionnaires and interviews with 36 class X DKV1 students. The analysis technique in this research uses descriptive analysis and thematic analysis. After data analysis, it can be concluded that implementing Kahoot! and the Windows Shopping model has a positive influence on students' interest in learning as evidenced by the results of questionnaire analysis & interviews which state that every aspect of interest in learning (Happy, Interested, Attentive, Involved) is fulfilled and gets positive perceptions from all students.

Keywords: *Interest Learning, Kahoot!, Windows Shopping Learning Model*

JGHTT (Journal of Global Hospitality and Tourism Technology)

Vol 1 Issue 1 2024

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.12590454](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12590454)

Received: 04/06/24 Revised: 15/06/24 Accepted: 28/06/24 Online: 29/06/24

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Introduction

Interest in learning is one of the things that needs to be considered in designing effective learning (Schiefele, 1991). Whether a lesson is effective or not can be seen from the student's learning outcomes, where one of the factors that influences the success of students in learning is interest in learning. (Wicaksono & Purwanti, 2019). Someone who has an interest in a subject will naturally feel happy and enthusiastic when taking part in learning. Therefore, to increase students' interest in learning, a teacher should ideally have a deep understanding of the material being taught and expertise in conveying it through effective teaching strategies. (Indra, 2017).

Based on observations and teaching assistance that had been previously carried out for Class X Basic DKV Students at SMK N 3 Surakarta in the Basic DKV subject, it is still found that some students tend to be less motivated in participating in learning, this is shown by the attitude of students who carry out activities of talking alone with their peers, are busy playing with their cellphones, or fall asleep in class. This needs to be considered, considering that learning motivation is one of the factors that encourages students' interest in learning so that effective learning goals can be achieved (Sandri & Tisnawati, 2023).

Several factors cause students' lack of interest in learning, one of which is that the learning model that the author provides at the beginning of the assistance is still considered conventional, whereas today's students are 21st-century students containing generation Z, where this generation has been accustomed to technology since childhood and has advanced mindset (Zubaidah, 2019) and don't like just sitting in class for too long (Anugrah et al., 2022). Apart from that, student 21 must also have the 4C competencies, namely creativity, communication skills, critical thinking and problem-solving, and Collaboration. (Vivekanandan, 2019). This is what makes today's students competitive and critical, and prefer to work in groups (Mardhiyah et al., 2021)

Various studies have been carried out to increase students' interest in learning. Increasing interest in learning aims to improve student learning outcomes and find effective learning models (Wicaksono & Purwanti, 2019). As in research (Nengsih, 2022) where the application of the Window Shopping learning model is suitable for 21st-century learning and increases students' interest in critical thinking and transferring knowledge. and solving. Negara (2020) also stated that the use of the Window Shoping learning model can develop creativity and increase students' interest in learning. Using the Window Shopping learning model can also increase learning motivation (Budiyanto, 2023) as well as student learning outcomes (Maryana, 2023)

Apart from learning models, learning media can also influence students' interest in learning, such as research conducted by (Tualaka & Sitompul, 2023) where to use the learning media Kahoot! can foster students' interest in learning as evidenced by changes in students' responses to becoming enthusiastic, active, enthusiastic, and following the teacher's instructions. This is in line with research (Rafnis, 2019) which states that Kahoot! is an interesting learning media that can make the learning atmosphere enjoyable. Kahoot! It is also equipped with audio, scores and time that can train students to compete healthily when playing it (Irwan et al., 2019).

Based on several studies related to research that has been carried out, this research will evaluate the effect of using Kahoot! and the Windows Shopping learning model to increase the learning interest of class X DKV1 students at SMK N 3 Surakarta in the Basic DKV subjects.

Research Method

This research was conducted on 36 class X DKV1 students at SMK N 3 Surakarta. The subject in this research is Even Semester DKV Basics related to Typography. The learning design development was carried out by adopting Windows Shopping and Kahoot! learning model activities. as a learning medium for the Quiz. The following activity plan was developed.

Table 1 Learning Activity Plan

No	Activity
Core activities	
1	Students are made into groups
2	The teacher conveys the initial material to be studied
3	The teacher divides the tasks to be given to each group through randomization
4	In groups, students discuss preparing the material
5	Each group determines the role of its members, there are those who serve as presenters, note takers, and members who are visitors to other groups
6	After completing the tour, members will return to their group and share information regarding the material they found

7	The teacher walks around to see things that need improvement, as well as giving students time to better understand the material
8	Implementation of the Quiz using Kahoot!
Closing Activities	
1	The teacher provides feedback and evaluations of the results of group work and quizzes

In this Windows Shopping learning model, students are made relaxed and comfortable, there are those who serve as Presenters (Sellers), namely those whose role is to explain the material when other group members go around, and there are those who serve as members (Buyers) who go around visiting each group. Use of Kahoot! It is also made as interesting as possible so that students will be more enthusiastic about working and competing healthily regarding the material they have studied.

Method

The method used in this research is a qualitative method, with this method researchers can further explore and understand individual and group perceptions (Creswell, 2014). Qualitative methods are used in the form of questionnaires & interviews with students. This question is intended to find out whether the use of Kahoot! and the Windows Shopping model influences students' learning interest. The instrument in this research questionnaire adopts and develops aspects of learning interest from research (Rohhadi, 2021) namely: (1) Feelings of joy; (2) Student interest; (3) Student attention; and (4) Student involvement

Table 2 Instrument Grid

No	Assessment Aspects	Indicator
1	Feelings of joy	- Learning the Windows Shopping model is fun - Use of Kahoot! pleasant
2	Student interest	- Be enthusiastic when learning using models Windows Shopping - Get excited when Quiz using Kahoot!
3	Student attention	- Listen carefully to directions and materials - Enthusiastic when using Kahoot!
4	Student involvement	- Be serious when playing in Windows Shopping - Always take the Kahoot! Quiz

The interviews in this research are intended to obtain information from only one point of view, so it is important to see the existence of asymmetric relationships. Researchers tend to direct interviews towards participants' perceptions and thoughts. It is hoped that with these interviews, researchers will be able to find out more about students' views regarding the use of Kahoot! & Windows Shopping model in learning.

Data Analysis Techniques

The data analysis technique in this research uses qualitative descriptive data analysis techniques to determine the effect of implementation. In this research, the data analysis carried out included:

Descriptive Analysis

Data analysis was obtained from the results of the questionnaire instrument. The qualitative data is then converted into quantitative form with the following conditions:

Table 3 Instrument Assessment Scores (Alreck & Settle, 1995)

Criteria	Score
Strongly agree	5
Agree	4
Doubtful	3
Don't agree	2
Strongly Disagree	1

After obtaining the quantitative data results from the questionnaire, the next step is to analyze the descriptive data to become an assessment classification for each aspect.

Table 4 Assessment Criteria for Each Aspect (Widoyoko, 2009)

Score	Category
> 4,2	Very good
3,4 - 4,2	Good
2,6 - 3,4	Enough
1,8 - 2,6	Not enough
< 1,8	Very less

Thematic Analysis

Thematic analysis was used on interview transcripts and focused on examining themes within the data (Boyatzis, 1998). Thematic analysis was carried out on students to determine perceptions regarding the use of Kahoot! and Windows Shopping models. The steps for thematic analysis in this research are as follows.

Figure 1 Thematic Analysis Steps

Result and Analysis

The research was conducted when the author implemented the PPL phase 1 PPG pre-service program at SMK N 3 Surakarta. In this research, the subjects taught were DKV Basics with material related to Typography. The following is documentation when learning the Windows Shopping model takes place

Figure 2 Windows Shopping Learning Process

After the implementation of Windows Shopping is complete, the group member on duty will present the material obtained to the group member on duty (as presenter). At the end of the lesson, a quiz was held using Kahoot! by using a Smartphone/PC and displayed on the projector regarding questions and live scores.

Figure 3 Implementation of the Quiz using Kahoot!

Description of Questionnaire Data

Based on the results of questionnaire data processing, there are the following results:

Table 4 Questionnaire Data

Indicator	Item	Score	Number of Respondents Who Voted	Percentage	Average Score
Feelings of joy	1	4	8	22,22%	4,7
		5	28	77,78%	
	2	4	5	13,89%	4,8
		5	31	86,11%	
Interest	1	4	10	27,78%	4,7
		5	26	72,22%	
	2	3	1	2,78%	4,8
		4	5	13,89%	
		5	30	83,33%	
		5	30	83,33%	
Attention	1	4	9	25%	4,75
		5	27	75%	
	2	4	12	33,33%	4,6
		5	24	66,67%	
Involvement	1	4	11	30,56%	4,6
		5	25	69,44%	
	2	4	19	52,78%	4,4
		5	17	47,22%	

Feelings of joy Indicator

Based on table 4, in the first & second items of the questionnaire, 100% of all respondents had a positive assessment tendency with an average score of 4.7 & 4.8 (Very Good). So, it can be concluded that the application of Kahoot! & Windows Shopping is good/fulfilled in terms of Feelings of joy Indicator

Interest Indicator

Based on table 4, in the first item all 100% of respondents had a positive assessment tendency with an average score of 4.7 (Very Good). Likewise, in the second item, 35 students (97.22%) also had a positive assessment tendency with an average score of 4.8 (Very Good). So, it can be concluded that the application of Kahoot! & Windows Shopping is good/fulfilled in terms of Interest Indicators.

Attention Indicator

Based on table 4, in the first & second items of the questionnaire, 100% of all respondents had a positive assessment tendency with an average score of 4.75 & 4.6 (Very Good). So, it can be concluded that the application of Kahoot! & Windows Shopping is good/fulfilled in terms of Attention Indicators

Involvement Indicators

Based on table 4, in the first & second items of the questionnaire, 100% of all respondents had a positive assessment tendency with an average score of 4.6 & 4.4 (Very Good). So it can be concluded that the application of Kahoot! & Windows Shopping is good/fulfilling in terms of Involvement Indicators

Thematic Analysis

This analysis was carried out to process interview transcripts for 36 students. In carrying out thematic analysis, the stages that must be carried out are the process of developing codes, coding interview transcripts, and taking abstracts. The code developed is as follows:

Feelings of joy

In mapping, categorization and analysis at the next stage, this parameter has the identity as code C1. This parameter is met if the participant expresses or shows some or all of the following behaviors

- Respondents' perception is that they are happy with the Windows Shopping model learning
- Respondents' perception is that they enjoy using Kahoot!

Interest

In mapping, categorization and analysis at the next stage, this parameter has the identity as code C2. This parameter is met if the participant expresses or shows some or all of the following behaviors

- Respondents' perception of being enthusiastic about participating in the Windows Shopping model learning
- Respondents' perception of being Interest about using Kahoot!

Attention

In mapping, categorization and analysis at the next stage, this parameter has the identity as code C3. This parameter is met if the participant expresses or shows some or all of the following behaviors

- Perception of respondents listening carefully to directions and materials
- Respondents' perceptions are enthusiastic about using Kahoot!

Involvement

In mapping, categorization and analysis at the next stage, this parameter has the identity as code C4. This parameter is met if the participant expresses or shows some or all of the following behaviors

- Respondents' perception is serious when playing a role in the Windows Shopping model
- Respondents' perception of always taking quizzes using Kahoot!

Thematic Analysis Digest

After carrying out the coding process and the thematic analysis stage that has been carried out on the interview data, the essence of each aspect of Learning Interest is obtained as follows:

Feelings of joy Aspect

The Feelings of joy Aspect obtained from interviews with students is that the Windows Shopping model presentation is a fun learning method because you can ask your peers about the material, as well as use Kahoot! It's fun because we compete and find out other students' points.

Interest Aspects

The aspect of interest obtained from interviews with students is that the use of the Windows Shopping model makes it easier for students to understand the material than the usual method, besides that students become serious about winning the Kahoot Quiz! because there is interesting competition

Attention Aspect

The aspect of attention obtained from interviews with students is that the use of the Windows Shopping model encourages students to listen carefully and can ask questions directly to the presenter if there is something they do not understand. Apart from that, using Kahoot! train students to stay focused.

Involvement Aspect

The involvement aspect was obtained from interviews with students, namely the use of Windows Shopping to train the cohesiveness of all group members to coordinate and understand the material. Apart from that, using Quiz Kahoot! Students are always awaited at the end of each lesson.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the analysis of the questionnaire and interview data, it can be concluded that implementing Kahoot! and the Windows Shopping model has a positive influence on students' interest in learning as evidenced by the results of questionnaire & interview analysis which that every aspect of learning interest (Feelings of joy, Interested, Attentive, Involved) is fulfilled and gets positive perceptions from all students. This is in line with research (Budiyanto, 2023; Negara, 2020; Nengsih, 2022) where the use of the Windows Shopping model can increase student interest and motivation to learn. Apart from that, Tualaka and Sitompul (2023) in their research also concluded that the use of Kahoot! can foster students' interest in learning. This is because Kahoot! is an interesting learning medium that makes the learning atmosphere enjoyable (Irwan et al., 2019).

Even though there has been a positive influence, there is a note that implementing Kahoot! and the Windows Shopping model can maximize, among other things, conditioning the classroom/Lab atmosphere so that it is conducive and orderly when learning the Windows Shopping model, apart from that the internet connection also influences the smooth implementation of Quiz using Kahoot!.

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